

A Comparative Study of Various Simulation Tools for Cognitive Radio Networks

Anjali Gupta^{#1}, Dr. Brijendra Kumar Joshi^{#2}

¹ *Electrical and Electronics Engineering Department,
Shri Vaishnav Vidyapeeth Vishwavidyalaya, Indore, India*

² *Electronics & Telecommunication and Computer Engineering,
Military College of Telecommunication Engineering, MHOW (MP), India*

¹ chitraanjali@yahoo.com

² brijendrajoshi@yahoo.com

Abstract

In the recent years with the wireless world facing a scarcity of radio spectrum, Cognitive Radio Networks (CRNs) have emerged as a very fascinating technology. The requirement for bandwidth and speed is increasing very fast with developing technology day by day. So, this problem has to be overcome in a more intelligent way whereby using the unused spectrum of the licensed users by the unlicensed users. A CRN can be simulated using various tools such as MATLAB, ns2, ns3, GNU Radio etc. In this paper we presented a comprehensive study of the above mentioned tools in CRN.

Keywords: CRN, primary user, secondary user, ns2, ns3, GNU Radio, MATLAB.

I. Introduction

The Cognitive Radio (CR) learns from its environment and changes its operating parameters accordingly. The radio spectrum is categorized into three categories namely White, Grey and Black spaces. Black spaces are part of the licensed spectrum which is used by the primary users or high power signals. Grey spaces are temporarily occupied by low power signals. White spaces are purely unutilized part of the licensed radio spectrum [1].

Cognitive Radio has the potential to utilize these Grey and White available spectrum spaces and utilize the unused or inefficiently used spectrum in a more intelligent way thus reducing the problem of spectrum shortage. The sensing, sharing, management and mobility of spectrum are the different parts of a cognitive radio network [2]. Here, the secondary users which are the unlicensed spectrum users try to occupy the spectrum left unused by the primary users which are

the licensed users. In *Spectrum Sensing*, CR searches for the spectrum holes or white spaces. The selection of the best available frequency band or channel is termed as *Spectrum Management*. When the secondary user shares the unused spectrum either utilizing any of the methods i.e. underlay, overlay and interweave, it is known as *Spectrum Sharing*. *Spectrum Mobility* is defined as the property of the cognitive radio to leave the occupied radio spectrum whenever any primary user tries to reschedule its activity. The figure 1 shows a simple model of Cognitive Radio Network.

Figure 1 A simple model of CRN

A CRN has three main system models on which primary and secondary user activity depends upon. These are: Underlay, Overlay and Interweave models.

Underlay system: In this secondary and primary user transmits simultaneously by maintaining interference at primary receiver by secondary users below certain threshold level [3] [4]. Here, the interference problem can be solved by using multiple antennas by which

secondary user transmission could be guided away from primary receiver. Also, we can use wide bandwidth on which secondary transmitter could be spread while dispreading signals at secondary receiver.

Overlay system: In these systems interference is reduced and sometimes completely cancelled as the primary users assist the secondary user for simultaneous transmission by using portion of their transmitting power.

Interweaver system: This system works on the primary idea of CR. They sense the unused spectrum opportunistically, utilize it for communication and leave the spectrum when primary user is detected. Thus avoids the considerable interference.

The secondary user does not affect the transmission of primary user, it may use either of the models of acquiring the primary channel i.e., underlay model, overlay model or interweaver model. For this the secondary user first recognizes the spectrum availability on the spatial, temporal or frequency domains, which means the absence of primary user. For this some of the communication-based regulations are also to be followed by the secondary user.

Today, computer-based simulation tools are more widespread in place of real platform based experimental analysis as these simulation tools are more cost effective and available as open-source software that can be easily installed on our computers. These Tools are updated with wireless communication libraries from time to time by different working groups as technology evolves. These simulators can be modeled for large scale simulations (scalable) where this is a major disadvantage when working on experiment based platforms. Results can be obtained with varying various parameters according to the need and radio environment. The paper provides an overview of the currently available CRN simulators.

Section II explains the cognitive radio transceiver architecture. Section III comprises of various simulation tools and their comparative analysis.

II. Cognitive Radio Architecture

The figure 2 shows the architecture of a cognitive radio where the complete system comprises of a front end radio (Transmit and Receive unit with the Analog to Digital conversion), baseband processing, and data processing unit (Interface between the front end and the user).

Figure 2 Architecture of a CRN

The cognitive radio network architecture is of three types mainly Infrastructure based, Ad-Hoc architecture and Mesh architecture. The transmission activities of the primary and secondary users is controlled and coordinated by the cognitive radio base stations in an infrastructure based networks. In Ad-Hoc networks the communication is one by adopting point to point connections using different communication protocols. The third one is heterogeneous network making a combination of the other two types. Therefore, a CR transceiver with the above defined architecture and network model should be able to sense and select the best available channel allocation strategy for communication between the secondary and primary users so that the interference levels are minimum.

III. Simulation Tools

There are a large variety of open source/licensed network simulators available e.g., ns2, ns3, MATLAB, GNU Radio etc. The network simulator used must be efficient in terms of total memory that is occupied by them during the simulation of any network, the time which is utilized for computing the required parameters

of the defined network time and how much the processor is utilized during the complete simulation.

When it comes to selection of any of the simulation software tools for research we must see that it is easy to use. It should be flexible for model development, modification and validation. It should be easier to install and configure the simulation software. Signal processing and data analysis should be done easily. Classification of network simulator is done according to the complexity of design, GUI support, scalability, analysis of traffic between various network nodes, network parameters such as throughput, delay, channel utilization etc [5].

Network Simulator 2 (ns2)

It is designed as an open-source simulator. Ns2 is used as a discrete event network simulator. ns2 is designed using C++ and it provides the simulation interface through OTcl which is the object-oriented language of Tcl. Network topology is described by writing OTcl scripts. The ns2 program code simulates that topology with some specified parameters. Network Animator (NAM) is a GUI for graphical view of network [6]. The basic functionalities of ns2 include the design of routing protocols, performance analysis of different networks, study of network traffic and designing of physical as well as network layer architectures.

While using ns2 these days, other specific packages for CRN have also been developed, such as Cognitive Radio Cognitive Networks (CRCN), CogNS and CRAHNS. All these packages have to be integrated with the ns2 protocol stack.

But overall, we can say that ns2 is a complex system containing large number of functional modules, which need recompilation each time if there is an update or addition in the system structure. As it is designed with languages C++ and Tcl, it becomes difficult to understand. Lastly, it has an overhead of large execution time.

Network Simulator 3 (ns3)

It is a new development and is again an open source discrete event network simulator. Its core language is C++ and Python. ns2 is not extended to ns3 but basically ns3 is a replacement of ns2. ns3 does not have an OTcl API [7] [8]. Its latest version supports parallel

simulation. Simulation as well as Emulation both can be performed in ns3 using sockets, where emulation mode integration with real networks is allowed. Some tools like Wireshark may be used to read the trace files and analyze network traffic. It has realistic environment and its source code is also well organized. ns2 and ns3 have many similarities in terms of framework, protocol stack, simulation support and application library. But it can be more advantageous than ns2 due to its more scalable and modular nature.

Table 1 shows the basic comparison between ns2 and ns3 on the basis of some features.

Table 1 Comparison between ns2 and ns3 Simulators

Features	ns2	ns3
Performance	Simulation time is more to make a link between C++ & OTcl	Less due to removal of overheads
Packet Representation	Complex	Simple
Memory Management	Memory required to store packets is not freed until the simulation is terminated	Better in ns3 as the system doesn't store the unneeded parameters and the packets do not contain the unused reserved header space
GUI	NAM the Animation system provides the visual representation of the network	PyViz is Python based real time visualization package
Robustness	Two language system makes debugging more complex	Single language system makes it more robust in long term
Contribution	Large amount of contributed code by users and design groups	Limited number of contributed codes

GNU Radio

It is a free and open source software development toolkit that provides signal processing blocks to implement software radio e.g. modulators, filters, amplifiers etc. GNU Radio applications are written using Python

programming language [9]. The signal processing part is implemented in C++. Simplified Wrapper and Interface Generator (SWIG) is used as the interface compiler which allows the integration between C++ and Python language. GNU Radio is modular and flexible. GNU Radio applications are built using Flowgraphs and Blocks. Blocks are the nodes of the Flowgraph [10] [11] [12]. The data flows through the edges. The signal processing part of the Flowgraph is done within the blocks. GRC (GNU Radio Companion) is the graphical user interface of GNU Radio. It allows us to build the Flowgraphs.

The signal processing blocks of GNU Radio are linked together for simulating some radio configurations. Universal Software Radio Peripheral (USRP) is the link between the radio and the real environment [13]. USRP consists of Analog-Digital Converter and Digital-Analog Converter, to convert some parameters from analog to digital domain and vice-versa.

GNU Radio is a user-friendly tool for the beginners. Here, by modifying the top level design or developing and implementing new functional blocks, and customizing the connections various research operations can be performed. This increases its flexibility and makes it more comprehensive to use for cognitive radio networks. GNU Radio has an ever growing popularity due to its good community support and real time environment support through the use of Software Defined Radio (SDR) and USRP [14]. A generic GNU Radio loop like as given in figure 3.

Figure 3 GNU Radio Components

MATLAB/-Simulink

This tool has the most widespread use in academics and research due to its powerful mathematical toolboxes. Matrix Laboratory known as MATLAB has the inbuilt blocks for signal processing. MATLAB is software that can be used to perform analysis and solve variety of mathematical and engineering problems. Programming in MATLAB is easy and very user friendly as it has extensively developed function library. Also, the graphics part is very well developed.

Simulink is an integrated part of MATLAB. System models are developed in the form of block diagrams and can be simulated and analyzed.

We can compare both the tools on basis of different features [17] [18] [19] [20] as given in Table 2:

Table 2 Comparison of MATLAB & GNU Radio

Features	MATLAB	GNU Radio
Real-time vs. Off-line	Generally, Matlab code is simulated for offline analysis, may be used with Universal Software Radio Peripheral	Often used for real-time analysis
Graphical vs. Non-Graphical flow graph	Need Simulink for graphical mode to work. In Simulink flow graphs all links are in black color.	(GRC) is the native graphical tool for GNU Radio. In GRC flowgraphs various data types are represented with different color.
Native language vs. Compiled language	Real-time analysis of MATLAB code is first translated into C-code and then compiled, with the help of tools like MATLAB Coder or Simulink Coder.	Python coding is used to build the flow graphs, which does not want compilation before execution for real-time analysis. All GNU Radio features are fully supported.
USRP support	Doesn't support legacy USRP	Driver support better on USRP

MATLAB has a wide range of Toolboxes. We can build a software defined and cognitive radio in MATLAB/-Simulink to analyze or study the different spectrum sensing, management and sharing techniques [15] [16].

IV. Conclusion

GNU Radio with GRC as a tool is a good option if we have an USRP support and good skills in Python, C++ and signal processing applications. Also if we are working in Spectrum sensing from physical layer point of view GNU Radio is a good option. As it already has an implemented example for Spectrum Sensing. Otherwise MATLAB is good for communication environment. ns2 and ns3 are open-source simulators but have installation issues and require patches and updating from the repositories.

V. References

- [1] Van Tam Nguyen, Frederic Villain, Yann Le Guillou, "Cognitive Radio RF: Overview and Challenges", Hindawi Publishing Corporation VLSI Design, Volume 2012, Article ID 716476, 13 pages.
- [2] Goutam Ghosh, Prasun Das, Subhajit Chatterjee, "Cognitive Radio and Dynamic Spectrum Access—A Study", International Journal of Next-Generation Networks (IJNGN), Vol.6, No.1, March 2014.
- [3] Beibei Wang, K. J. Ray Liu, "Advances in Cognitive Radio Networks: A survey", IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing, Vol. 5, No. 1, February 2011.
- [4] Purnendu S. M. Tripathi, Ashok Chandra, Ramjee Prasad, "Deployment of Cognitive Radio in India", Wireless Pers Commun, 76:523–533, Published online: 17 April 2014, Springer Science+Business Media New York.
- [5] Suraj G. Gupta, Mangesh M. Ghonge, Parag D. Thakare, Dr. P. M. Jawandhiya, "Open-Source Network Simulation Tools: An Overview", International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Engineering & Technology (IJARCET), Vol. 2, Issue 4, April 2013, ISSN: 2278 – 1323.
- [6] Uma R Pujeri, Dr. V Palanisamy, "Survey of Various Open Source Network Simulators", International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR), Vol. 3 Issue 12, December 2014, ISSN: 2319-7064.
- [7] Atta ur Rehman Khana, Sardar M. Bilalb, Mazliza Othmana, "A Performance Comparison of Open Source Network Simulators for Wireless Networks", 2012 IEEE International Conference on Control System, Computing and Engineering, 23 - 25 Nov. 2012, Penang, Malaysia, pp. 34-38.
- [8] Elias Weingartner, Hendrik vom Lehn and Klaus Wehrle, "A performance comparison of recent network simulators", IEEE International Conference on Communications, July 2009, ICC '09.
- [9] GNU Radio, the free and open software radio ecosystem. Online: <https://gnuradio.org>.
- [10] A. M. Wyglinski, M. Nekovee, Y. T. Hou, "Cognitive Radio Communications and Networks: Principles and Practice", Elsevier, December, 2009.
- [11] Mohd Adib Sarijari, Arief Marwanto, Norsheila Faisal, Sharifah Kamilah Syed Yusof, Rozeha A. Rashid, Muhammad Haikal Satria, "Energy Detection Sensing based on GNU Radio and USRP: An Analysis Study", IEEE 9th Malaysia International Conference on Communications 15-17 Dec. 2009, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia.
- [12] Rozeha A. Rashid, M. Adib Sarijari, N. Faisal, S. K. S. Yusof, N. Hija Mahalin, A. C. C. Lo, "Spectrum Sensing Measurement using GNU Radio and USRP Software Radio Platform", ICWMC 2011: The Seventh International Conference on Wireless and Mobile Communications, ISBN: 978-1-61208-140-3, pp. 237-242.
- [13] M. Ettus, Universal software radio peripheral. <http://www.ettus.com>.
- [14] GNU Radio API list, <http://gnuradio.org/doc/doxygen/index.html>
- [15] D. Shin, "A Dictionary of the GNU Radio blocks", 21 August 2005.
- [16] Anurag Bansal, Ms. Rita Mahajan, "Building Cognitive Radio System Using MATLAB", International Journal of Electronics and Computer Science Engineering, ISSN 2277-1956, Vol.1, No.3, pp. 1555-1560.
- [17] Eeru R. Lavudiya, Dr. K.D. Kulat, Jagdish D. Kene, "Implementation and Analysis of Cognitive Radio System using MATLAB", International Journal of Computer Science and Telecommunications, Volume 4, Issue 7, July 2013, ISSN 2047-3338.
- [18] Md. Manjurul Hasan Khan, Dr. Paresh Chandra Barman, "Investigation of Cognitive Radio System Using MATLAB", World Vision, Vol. 8, No. 1, Nov 2014, ISSN: 2078-8460.
- [19] Goutam Ghosh, Prasun Das, Subhajit Chatterjee, "Simulation and Analysis of Cognitive Radio System Using MATLAB", International Journal of Next-Generation Networks (IJNGN) Vol.6, No.2, pp. 31-45, June 2014.
- [20] Salma Ibrahim, AL haj Mustafa, Amin Babiker, A/Nabi Mustafa, "Simulation of Cognitive Radio System Using MATLAB", IOSR Journal of Electrical and Electronics Engineering (IOSR-JEEE), e-ISSN: 2278-1676, p-ISSN: 2320-3331, Volume 10, Issue 3 Ver. I, May – Jun. 2015, pp. 28-32.